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METHODOLOGY FOR FILLING PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN WITH UNFORMED ROOTS

Abstract

Treatment of caries is one of the main tasks in dentistry, as effective treatment prevents the development of complications, such as secondary caries. About 40% of all dental interventions are associated with secondary and recurrent caries, which takes up a third of the doctor's working time. Studies show that the development of secondary caries depends on the characteristics of fillings and local resistance of hard dental tissues. Traditional methods of prevention include proper cavity preparation, selection and use of materials, compliance with filling technology and hygiene of interdental spaces. For pediatric dental treatment, the problem of finding new technologies is relevant, including the use of fluoride-containing glass ionomer cements (GIC) with an increased fluoride content. The study involved 90 children aged 7-12 years with different levels of enamel resistance to caries. A new technique of minimally invasive treatment using GIC Argion Molar AC and a method of deep fluoridation with the drug Glufluored was used. The sensitivity of hard dental tissues to acids and the effectiveness of methods in the clinic were studied.

Key words: *deep fluoridation, secondary caries, dry cotton swab, blue color, VOCO, dental treatment*

The problem of treating dental caries is one of the main ones in dentistry. Effective and high-quality treatment of caries prevents the development of complications - secondary caries [1, 4, 7, 9, 10]. About 40% of all therapeutic dental measures related to dental treatment are carried out in connection with secondary and recurrent caries, which takes up a third of the dentist's working time [11, 12]. Many researchers agree that the development of secondary caries is influenced by a number of factors associated with the properties of fillings (restorations) and local resistance of hard dental tissues. Therefore, traditional methods of preventing secondary caries remain adherence to the principles of cavity preparation, rational selection and correct use of filling materials, adherence to filling technology and hygiene of interdental spaces [2, 3, 6, 8, 11]. Dentistry today is an intensively developing branch of medicine. It uses the most modern technologies for the creation of effective high-quality restorative materials and high speed turbine machines. But, despite this, pronounced emotional excitability, intolerance of any pain, which can cause demophobia, and refusal of any dental interventions are typical of children [2, 4, 7, 12]. In this regard, the problem of finding new technologies for treating carious cavities remains relevant [6, 10-12]. One of the factors determining the remineralization of hard dental tissues is fluorine (Knappvost A., 2005). It is known that glass ionomer cements (GIC) have the maximum release of fluoride ions, therefore the development of GIC with increased fluoride content is an important task. In addition, GIC provides a higher level of connection with dental tissues [1, 2, 5, 8]. The study of the properties and mechanism of action of GIC with increased fluoride content on hard dental tissues, as well as the study of the effectiveness of their use in the clinic with a minimally invasive method of preparation is of

practical interest and is a topical problem of therapeutic dentistry. The purpose of the study: choosing the optimal method for treating caries of permanent teeth in children during the period of root formation at different levels of caries resistance (CR) of enamel. MATERIALS AND METHODS To accomplish the objectives, 90 schoolchildren aged 7-12 years were examined during the period of eruption of permanent teeth and the formation of their roots. A new technology of tooth preparation was studied: a minimally invasive method followed by filling with glass ionomer cement Argion Molar AC (VOCO, Germany), delayed filling using the deep fluoridation method, determination of the CR of tooth enamel in children using the enamel resistance test (TER test). A standard dental examination was carried out in children, and the condition of hard dental tissues to acid exposure was assessed using the TER test (Okushko V.R., Kosareva L.I., Lutskaya I.K., 1983). According to this method, the central incisor of the upper jaw was cleaned of soft plaque with a 1% solution of H₂O₂ and dried with a dry cotton swab. Etching acid was applied with a pipette to the middle of the vestibular surface of the incisor with a diameter of 1.5-2.0 mm for 2-3 seconds. Then the etching was removed with a dry cotton swab and stained with a 2% methylene blue solution. The dye was removed with a dry cotton swab using rubbing movements, completely removing it from the enamel surface. The etched area was stained blue of varying intensity. A 10-point typographic shade scale of blue was used to assess the staining intensity. With a staining intensity of 1 to 3 points, the examined children were classified as having high caries resistance, 4-5 points — moderate, 6-7 points — low, and more than 8 points — very low caries resistance (maximum risk of caries). When treating teeth in children with moderate and deep

caries with reduced enamel CR for remineralization, we used the method of deep fluoridation of enamel and dentin with the drug Gluftored (VladMiVa, Belgorod). This preparation includes the sequential application of liquids of different compositions: a defatted carious cavity is moistened with an applicator soaked in the liquid for the first smudging and left for 30 seconds (the cavity is dried with air), and then smudging is carried out in the same way with the second liquid. It is also dried with a stream of air. With deep fluoridation, due to the high solubility of microcrystals, high local concentrations of fluoride ions are created on the tooth surface (approximately 100 mg / l). Since the rate of remineralization is proportional to the square of the concentration of fluoride ions, deep fluoridation leads to an increase in the remineralization rate by 100 times more than other fluoride salts. With this method, it is unnecessary to use other linings under the filling materials. The deep fluoridation method was repeated 2-3 times with an interval of 1 week. The carious cavity was filled with aqueous dentin during this time. After the completion of the remineralizing therapy course, after 2-3 weeks, the aqueous dentin was replaced with a permanent filling made of Argion Molar AC glass ionomer cement. The essence of the minimally invasive therapy method is the early diagnosis of caries, minimal surgical intervention in the tooth tissues, followed by filling with glass ionomer cement. Preparation of hard dental tissues with the minimally invasive method is recommended to be carried out under the control of a caries detector. The caries detector operates on the basis of varying degrees of staining of dentine layers in the carious lesion. Since the outer layer of demineralized dentine is completely destroyed and consists of a mixture of pathologically smoothed collagen fibers and odontoblasts, it is stained brightly, while the inner layer is partially demineralized and stained much lighter, retaining the ability to remineralize. The composition of the caries detector: 0.5-1.0% solution of basic fuchsin in propylene glycol. The use of the caries detector promotes a gentle method of removing only non-viable tooth tissues and maximum preservation of tooth tissues capable of remineralization, thereby ensuring maximum duration of tooth viability. When using minimally invasive therapy methods, it is necessary to use modern filling materials that are resistant to physical stress, the action of mixed saliva, with a low modulus of elasticity, high adhesiveness, and good radiopacity. These requirements are met by Argion Molar AC glass ion citrate containing silver and releasing biologically active fluoride ions for a long time. Before the study, all children underwent full professional oral hygiene, and schoolchildren, their parents, and teachers were interviewed about the risk factors for caries. Motivation for high-quality oral hygiene, removal of dental plaque, and correction of mastering hygiene skills in dynamics were provided. **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION** When assessing the results of the TER test, it was found that out of 90 examined schoolchildren, only 18 (20%) had a high level of enamel CR, while the remaining 72 (80%) children had CR of varying levels. Thus, 24 (26.7%) of those examined had moderate CR, 27 (30%) had low CR, and 21 (23.3%) children had very low CR.

The majority of examined children (56.7%) had low or very low resistance of teeth to acid exposure, which predicts the development of multiple dental caries and requires a special approach to the treatment and prevention of dental caries. Children with different levels of CR were subsequently divided into 2 groups. In each group, depending on the CR of enamel, appropriate treatment was carried out. In group 1, molar caries was treated using the traditional method, i.e., preparation of the carious cavity according to Black, medical treatment with subsequent filling with Belatsin silicophosphate cement. In group 2, children with high and moderate CR and CR underwent traditional caries treatment, and with low and very low - a comprehensive therapeutic and prophylactic method. If surgical and restorative treatment is sufficient for the treatment of caries in children with high or moderate CR, then with low and very low levels of CR of tooth enamel, general and local pathogenetic therapy is also required. Under these conditions, a comprehensive therapeutic and prophylactic method was carried out in 3 directions:

1. Surgical and restorative treatment using microinvasive preparation after 3-4 sessions of reparative therapy with Gluftored and 2-3 lessons of oral hygiene. The carious cavity is filled with Argion Molar AC cement.
2. Local pathogenetic reparative therapy with Gluftored to strengthen the walls and bottom of the carious defect, prevent recurrence of caries and development of secondary caries before filling the carious cavity. After reparative therapy, the edges of the carious cavity were denser. Preference for restoration of the carious cavity was focused on preventive materials - glass ion ion glass ionizers with a high silver content and releasing active fluoride ions; Argion Molar AC met these requirements.
3. General pathogenetic therapy was aimed at normalizing impaired metabolic processes and increasing the nonspecific resistance of the body, increasing its resistance to the effects of general unfavorable factors. In collaboration with a pediatrician, the complex included rational nutrition, adherence to a daily routine, and the prescription of individualized drug therapy. For the examined children of primary school age, in consultation with a pediatrician, liquid calcium preparations, vitamin complexes, and probiotics were prescribed 2-3 times a day after meals. Remineralizing therapy was carried out using the deep fluoridation method. The method developed by Professor A. Knappwost allows obtaining crystals of particularly high dispersion, which are proportionate to the pores formed in the enamel [1, 3]. A total of 38 teeth were treated using the deep fluoridation method: 21 molars and 17 premolars. The results were compared after treatment of the examined subjects after 6, 12, and 24 months. In Group II, secondary caries development around the filling was not noted after 6 and 12 months, and minor complications in the form of secondary caries development appeared 24 months after filling. The second type of complication in the form of a violation of the marginal fit of the filling appeared in small quantities not earlier than 12 months ($1.2 \pm 0.7\%$) and after 24 months ($7.5 \pm 1.2\%$), which is 6.25 times more. In Group I, after 6 months, a complication in the form of secondary caries was noted in 6.7% of children. After

12 months, the frequency of secondary caries increased by 2.2 times, and after 24 months it reached 28.7%, which is 4.3 times higher compared to the initial value and almost 2 times more than 12 months ago. Violation of the marginal fit of fillings was noted already after 6 months (1.5%), after 12 months it increased 6 times, and after 24 months - another 3 times and reached 22.3%. Thus, analyzing the obtained data, we can conclude that with the standard treatment method, there was an increase in complications after filling a carious cavity in children with low and very low CR of tooth enamel for all the parameters studied. **CONCLUSION** In Group II, a comprehensive therapeutic and preventive approach to treatment was used, consisting of 3 directions. The drug Gluftored with the effect of deep mineralization was used, promoting the sealing of enamel microcracks, dentin tubules and cement. The resulting substance is a high-molecular polymer of silicic acid with submicroscopic crystals of calcium fluoride, magnesium fluoride and copper fluoride deposited in it. It is alkaline in nature and extremely dense, which ensures effective protection of dentin and pulp from the harmful effects of all agents, especially acids. Due to copper ions, the sealing lining has long-term bactericidal activity, constantly renewed under the influence of oxygen. Copper hydroxide included in the liquid has a more powerful disinfectant force than calcium hydroxide included in the composition of medicinal linings traditionally used in the treatment of deep caries. During deep fluoridation, the precipitated alkaline copper fluoride has a permanent bactericidal effect. The preparation applied to the bottom and walls of the cavity is capable of preventing secondary caries [1, 3], which was confirmed by the data obtained. Minimally invasive preparation method, delayed filling with secondary caries prevention and enamel remineralization with gluftored, followed by filling with Argion Molar AC glass ion ion citrate containing active fluoride ions, which continues to have a caries-preventive and remineralizing effect for up to two years of observation. Prescription of calcium preparations, vitamin complexes and probiotics helps to increase the child's immunity. This comprehensive approach to the treatment of permanent tooth caries in children turned out to be highly reliably effective during the period of tooth root formation and with low enamel caries resistance. The data obtained allow us to recommend the developed comprehensive approach to the treatment of permanent tooth caries in children for widespread use, with incomplete enamel mineralization in children during the period of root formation.

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